

A Formal Framework for Metamodeling in the Context of MDE

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Abstract: Metamodeling is a central concept in Model Driven Engineering (MDE). An important consideration in metamodeling is that secure metamodels are a prerequisite for secure software, since errors in a metamodel lead to errors in its instances (models). Formal methods can help solve this problem by providing systematic and rigorous techniques for reducing ambiguities and inconsistencies in the specification of metamodels. The goal of this article is to present a unified formal framework for metamodeling in the context of MDE, essentially based on MOF, the metamodeling foundation of the OMG industry standards. It is based on the Nereus metamodeling language and includes transformers for translating both MOF metamodels to Nereus metamodels and Nereus metamodels to MOF metamodels, with some prospects for future industrial use of these results. The Nereus language can be seen as a concrete syntax for MOF, extended by additional properties expressed by axioms. Transformers are defined starting from systems of transformation rules that allow automation of processes. An original real-world case in the context of model-driven reverse engineering is described.

Keywords: Model-Driven Engineering, Metamodeling, Formal Specification, Model-Driven Architecture, MOF, Formal Method

Categories: D.2.1, D.2.2, D.2.4, D.2.11, F.4.1

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1 Introduction

Metamodeling is a central concept in Model Driven Engineering (MDE). It plays an important role in the development of complex systems for specific contexts such as IoT, cloud computing, mobile computing, and artificial intelligence [Favre, 21-b]. In recent years, specific IoT or cloud computing MOF-like metamodels have emerged to support the systematic development of secure software. For example, the Open Cloud Computing Interface (OCCI) emerged to address the difficulties caused by the variety of cloud providers offering different resource management interfaces [Nyrén, 16], [Zalila, 23]. [Favre, 18], [Favre, 21-b] and [Favre, 22] describe the modernization of non-mobile software in the context of ADM [ADM, 25].

MDE is an approach to software development that focuses on using models to define highly automated software development processes based on reusable transformations between models that conform to metamodels. The OMG has adopted an architecture standard, Model-Driven Architecture (MDA), which uses models to guide the entire lifecycle of a system; all artifacts such as requirements specifications, architecture descriptions, design descriptions, and code are considered models. Metamodeling is an essential technique in MDA, based on the use of a metamodeling language called the

Meta Object Facility (MOF) [MOF, 19]. An important consideration regarding metamodeling is that to achieve secure systems it is a prerequisite to have secure metamodels, since errors in a metamodel lead to errors in its instances (models). Formal methods can help solve this problem by providing systematic and rigorous techniques for reducing ambiguities and inconsistencies in the software requirements specification.

Formal methods are controversial and are generally only used in the development of safety-critical and mission-critical software. However, behind the specifications and formal methods is a community that has developed a substantial body of research, tools, and case studies demonstrating that it is possible to use formal techniques to develop off-the-shelf software that is as reliable as any other engineering product. The use of formal methods can be cost-effective because defects are eliminated early or not introduced in the requirements specification, thus reducing the amount of rework needed later in development. Within the next few decades, tools based on verification will be as useful and widespread for software development in general as they are today in safety-critical systems.

We think it is a good idea to combine metamodeling with formal methods. This article presents a method for automatically creating secure metamodels in the context of MDE implementations like MDA. We describe a formal language for metamodeling called Nereus, which combines the best features of different algebraic languages. It is a concrete syntax for MOF with additional properties expressed by axioms. We translated Nereus into CASL, which has a complete formal semantics and can be integrated with theorem provers.

For decades, people have been trying to automatically generate software from formal specifications. One example is transformational programming, which has been attempting to automatically generate code from specifications since the 1990s. Since software generation is not currently done in the same way as code generation, and the focus has shifted from code generation based on model specifications to code generation based on metamodels, it is important to be able to automatically construct secure metamodels in both directions.

The objective of this work is to show an integration of previous results that have contributed to the definition of a unified framework for formal metamodeling in the context of MDE, essentially based on MOF metamodeling. It is based on the Nereus metamodeling language and includes transformers for translating both MOF metamodels to Nereus metamodels and Nereus metamodels to MOF metamodels. The integration of Nereus specifications with the CASL language is also described. This article presents extensions to the Nereus metamodeling language that facilitate the simulation of object-oriented systems modeled by UML and defined by instantiation of MOF metamodels. It aims to "close" the results from the theoretical point of view of the definition of a unified framework for formal metamodeling, which have evolved over the years until they have consolidated into a solid theoretical base. Although this article refers to and is based on previous work, it is the only one that presents in an integrated way a unified theoretical framework for formal metamodeling with some prospects for future industrial use of these results. Moreover, the article includes an original real-world application in the context of model-driven reverse engineering. We describe the TRACEM metamodel and how its Nereus specification could be integrated with MOF.

This article is organized as follows. Section 2 describes and introduces the basic concepts related to our proposal. Section 3 presents some relevant literature related to

our approach. Section 4 describes our contribution, a metamodel construction process that integrates three types of specifications: algebraic specifications expressed in the Nereus language, algebraic specifications expressed in the CASL language, and semiformal MOF metamodel specifications. Section 5 describes the syntax of Nereus in detail. This section includes two examples of specifications: the OCL Collection Class and the Package TRACEM Metamodel. Section 6 describes the semantics of Nereus with respect to CASL. Section 7 describes how to simulate object-oriented execution models from Nereus specifications. Section 8 describes how to bridge the gap from Nereus specifications to MOF metamodels. Section 9 describes how to transform MOF metamodels expressed as UML class diagrams annotated with OCL constraints into formal metamodels in Nereus. Finally, Section 10 presents general conclusions, and future work.

2 Background

A Model-Driven Engineering (MDE) is an approach to software development that focuses on the use of models to define highly automated software development processes based on reusable transformations between models that conform to metamodels. The idea behind MDE is that software development can be broken down into standardized, highly automated activities that can be used to mass-produce software applications, thereby reducing cost, development time, and risk.

There are several acronyms associated with model-driven development: MBE (model-based engineering), MDE (model-driven engineering), MDD (model-driven development), MDA (model-driven architecture), and ADM (architecture-driven modernization) [Favre, 10].

MBE is the branch of software engineering in which software models play an important role as the basis for development. However, there is no direct link between the models and the generated software, which is precisely defined by transformations. MDE can be seen as a subset of MBE. It is the branch of software engineering in which processes are driven by models, i.e. models are the primary artifacts of various software processes. MDD refers to forward engineering processes that use models as primary development artifacts. Model-Driven Architecture (MDA) is a specific implementation of MDD [MDA, 25]. MDA provides an approach for specifying a system independent of the platforms it supports, specifying platforms, selecting a specific platform for the system, and transforming the system specification into an implementation for the selected platform.

The evolution of MDE and MDA has accompanied paradigms such as cloud computing and the Internet of Things, which involve more complex and interconnected systems. In this context, metamodeling is an essential technique in MDA. MDA is based on the use of a metamodeling language called the Meta Object Facility (MOF) [MOF, 19]. MOF can be considered the essence of MDA, allowing different types of artifacts from different technologies to be used together in an interoperable way. Related OMG standard metamodels and meta-metamodels share a common design philosophy. All of them, including MOF, are expressed using MOF, which defines a common way to capture the full diversity of modeling standards and exchange constructs used in MDA. MOF metamodels must master two different languages: UML for expressing class diagrams that capture the structure of the domain, and the OCL

language for expressing the associated semantics [OCL, 14]. ADM is a set of modernization specifications developed within the OMG [ADM, 25].

3 Related Work

A formal specification technique must provide at least a syntax, some kind of semantics, and an inference system. The syntax defines the structure of the text of a formal specification, including properties expressed as axioms (formulas of some logic). The semantics describes the models associated with a given specification; in the context of formal specification, a model is a mathematical object that defines the behavior of the realizations of the specification. The inference system allows the definition of deductions that can be made from a formal specification. These deductions allow new formulas to be derived and verified. The inference system is central to the automation of testing, prototyping, or verification.

With the advent of object-oriented languages, new specification languages or extensions of formal languages to support object-oriented concepts began to emerge. Larch/Smalltalk was the first language with subtype and inheritance specification. Larch/C++ is another language with similar features [Leavens, 96]. JML is a way to formally describe the behavior and interfaces of Java classes and functions. It is based on formal specification and verification, which has aimed to bring value to Java programmers and allowed the development of tools such as Key, OpenJML, and others [Leavens, 22]. [Barnett, 11] describes the Spec# programming language, a formal language for API contracts influenced by JML which extends C# with constructs for formal contracts.

Subsequently, much work was done on semantics for UML/OCL models [OCL, 14]. With the advent of MDA, the integration of the MOF metalanguage with a formal specification technique began to be addressed. It is important to note that the instantiation of a metamodel produces models, which in turn are instantiated. Thus, errors in a metamodel lead to errors in its model instances. Current metamodeling tools allow code generation and detection of invalid constraints, but very little progress has been made in generating instances of the metalanguage.

Several works are related to the specification of metamodels based on different formalisms. Considering that MOF metamodels include a subset of UML class diagrams annotated in OCL, this section emphasizes work related to the formalization of MOF-like metamodels or UML class diagrams annotated in OCL. A metamodel specification must use two different languages: UML for capturing the domain structure and OCL for defining well-formedness rules. There are no guidelines to support metamodel construction across both language paradigms. [Cadavid, 15] observes that all metamodels tend to have a small subset of concepts constrained by the OCL rules, most of which are loosely coupled to the underlying structure.

A metamodel definition language called KM3 (Kernel Meta Meta Model), which can be considered as an extension of EMOF and allows attaching executable actions to EMOF metamodels, is presented in [Jouault,06]. However, KM3 is also designed to transcend technical domains and thus allows the definition of non-MOF metamodels.

[Boronat, 10] describes an algebraic, reflexive, and executable framework for metamodeling in MDD. The framework provides a formal semantics of the notions of metamodel, model, and conformance relation between a model and a metamodel. The

semantics is integrated into EMF as a plugin called MOMENT (MOdelmanageMENT). The formalism underlying MOMENT is MAUDE. Bridges between the MAUDE and EMF technology spaces have been defined.

[Barbier, 13] describes how to construct metamodels based on constructive logic, along with inherent proofs. A key contribution is a generative approach to constructing new metaclasses from existing ones. The authors propose to define the entire MOF in this way and implement it in Coq Proof Assistant (<https://coq.inria.fr/>). They do not aim at an automatic transformation from Coq to MOF-like metamodels.

An approach to metamodel formalization based on algebraic data types and Constraint Logic Programming (CLP) is described in [Jackson, 11]. Proofs and test case generation are encoded as CLP satisfiability problems and solved automatically. The authors describe the Formula framework for solving proofs to verify properties of the metamodels, which are viewed as instances of CLP. The Eclipse plug-in CD2FORMULA, which implements the translation of UML class diagrams into Formula in an MDA-aligned manner, is described in [Pérez, 14]. The proposed framework can be used to reason, validate and verify UML software designs by checking correctness properties and generating model instances using a model exploration tool based on Formula. The proposal does not support automatic translation of specific OCL constraints to Formula.

[Lano, 24] describes a new approach to program translation using MDE to reverse engineer programs into specifications in the UML and OCL formalisms, and then forward engineer the specifications to the required target language.

[Doller, 20] proposes a formal modeling language to specify metamodels called M2FOL. The formalized metamodel then rigorously defines the signature of a language and provide an algorithmic derivation of the formal modeling language from the metamodel.

One of the limitations of metamodel implementations is the generation of test instances. A graph grammar for solving this problem is described in [Erigh, 06]. An automatic method that guarantees to synthesize a diverse set of instances from a conceptual scheme by combining model finders, term classification, and constraint strengthening techniques is proposed in [Burgueño, 19]. This last approach is based on the principle of diversity guaranteed by a systematic generation of classifying terms that partition the solution space of a model into a set of equivalence classes. The proposal has been validated in the USE tool for UML/OCL.

An important issue related to metamodels is how to control their evolution. The problem of identifying, predicting, and evaluating the significance of the impact of metamodel changes on the existing artifacts is described in [Iovino, 12]. The approach is based on the concept of the megamodel. In [Jácome-Guerrero, 18] a framework that provides methodological support for the evolution of metamodels is proposed. A mechanism for specifying adaptation and extension rules for metamodels is proposed, as well as a tool for adapting metamodels according to such rules. Butting [18] defines a bridge between grammar-based languages and metamodel-based languages.

Other authors show the integration of formal methods and security development [Rouland, 19]. [Favre, 21-a] shows the theoretical foundations of a method for automatically constructing secure metamodels in the context of specific IoT or cloud computing metamodels. [Favre, 22] describes an integration of ADM, cross-platform development and formal metamodeling to face the migration of object-oriented software to mobile technologies through the Haxe language.

Considering that complex system specifications are large and difficult to reason with formal approaches, [Baak, 24] proposes a metamodel to describe the high-level concepts of software architectures in a component-port-connector fashion focusing on providing hierarchical modeling capabilities by considering the construction of composite components from existing ones.

3.1. Our Contribution

Our approach contributes to existing approaches in several ways. Nereus is a metamodeling formal language with strong abstraction from details of classical mathematical notation of algebraic languages. It is a formal notation close to the core concepts of MOF metamodels, allowing metadesigners who need to manipulate metamodels to understand their formal specification. Compared to formal algebraic languages, Nereus can use metamodel constructs, is easier to use, and can automate important issues (e.g., association specification), making the process of developing a formal specification simpler and more understandable compared to a "lower-level" algebraic language. A metadesigner can accurately reflect the MOF constructs in Nereus and delegate their translation to a translator, which automates the process. Compared to declarative, assertion-based languages such as OCL, we can say that these specifications are not as suitable as Nereus for specifying at the first design levels, they are valuable at levels closer to the implementations, to the code. However, Nereus aims to take advantage of both types of specifications by providing transformation rule systems to integrate Nereus with OCL. These systems are the basis for automation and are an original contribution respecting the existing ones. On the other hand, our approach is a contribution to the interoperability of formal languages. Considering that there are many formal algebraic languages, Nereus can be considered as an intermediate language, that allows to connect any number of source languages without having to define explicit metamodel transformations for each pair of languages. In general, the notion of polymorphism at the metamodel level is imprecise because it is not defined as a metamodel type. These are limitations for applications related to MDE. For example, subtyping has implications for the reuse of models, metamodels, and models. Another contribution of our approach is that metamodels are typed.

4 Formal Construction of MOF Metamodels

The metamodeling process integrates three types of specifications: algebraic specifications expressed in the Nereus metamodeling language, algebraic specifications expressed in the CASL algebraic language, and semiformal MOF metamodel specifications. Figure 1 shows the flow of specification analysis through the different steps of the process that integrates different types of specifications and the transformations between them.

First, the metadesigner writes a Nereus specification, which is analyzed by the Nereus analyzer and modified based on the results of this analysis, with the goal of obtaining a syntactically correct specification. The Nereus-To-CASL translator generates a CASL specification from the Nereus specification, which can be linked to Automatic Theorem Provers (ATPs) provided by HETS [Hets, 25]. ATPs allow to

perform a consistency analysis of the metamodel and to obtain an analyzed specification. The initial specification can be improved by reinjecting the changes introduced in the latter Nereus specification, and the metadesigner revises the specification as necessary. Finally, the validated Nereus specification can be automatically transformed into a MOF metamodel based on a set of transformation rules. The following sections describe the basis of this approach: the Nereus metamodeling language, the transformation from Nereus to CASL, and systems of transformation rules from Nereus metamodels to MOF metamodels specified in OCL and from MOF to Nereus.

Figure 1: Constructing Secure Metamodels

5 The Nereus Language

The Nereus language is a formal metamodeling language inspired by MOF. Thus, just like MOF, Nereus provides mechanisms for specifying classes, basic relationships, associations, and packages. At the same time, unlike other algebraic languages, it also provides several native types of UML-like relationships (dependency, binary association, aggregation, composition). The syntax of the Nereus language is described below.

```

CLASS className [<parameterList>]
IMPORTS <importList>
IS-SUBTYPE-OF <subtypeList>
INHERITS <inheritList>
ASSOCIATION <associationList>
BASIC CONSTRUCTORS <constructorList>
DEFERRED
TYPE(S) <sortList>
ATTRIBUTE(S) <attributeList>
OPERATION(S) <operationList>
EFFECTIVE
TYPE(S) <sortList>
ATTRIBUTE(S) <attributeList>
OPERATION(S) <operationList>
AXIOMS <varList>
<axiomList>
END-CLASS

```

Figure 2: The Nereus Class Syntax

5.1 The Nereus Syntax

5.1.1 Class Specification

The basic specification in Nereus is the class. Classes can declare types, attributes, operations and axioms, which are formulas of first-order logic. In addition, the language provides the possibility to parameterize these specifications, which gives more flexibility and allows the user of each class to restrict the data types of each parameter. Specifications are structured through various types of relationships, such as importing, inheritance, subtyping, and associations. Figure 2 shows the syntax of a Nereus class structured by basic relationships. The class contains IMPORTS, INHERITS, IS-SUBTYPE-OF, ASSOCIATION, BASIC CONSTRUCTORS, EFFECTIVE, DEFERRED, and AXIOMS clauses. The EFFECTIVE and DEFERRED clauses may also contain additional TYPES, ATTRIBUTES, and OPERATIONS subclasses. The different clauses are described below.

5.1.2 Relationships

Among the clauses corresponding to Nereus classes, there are those that define the relationships between classes. Each of them consists of a non-empty list of references to specifications with which these relationships are established. These related specifications contribute to the new definition, different components that are reused in different ways depending on the semantics of the clause to which they belong. In addition, each element included in one of these clauses can not only be a simple reference, but it can also be parameterized and have a renaming for one or more of its operations. Specifically, the relationship clauses are INHERITS, IS-SUBTYPE-OF, IMPORTS, and ASSOCIATES. The remaining components of the new specification that do not come from any of these clauses, that is, those that are defined "from scratch"

in the new class (operations, attributes, and axioms), are called the "own part" of the class. The IMPORTS clause is used to express dependencies. The interpretation of this relationship is that the new specification makes use of the imported specifications that do not belong to its own part. The INHERITS clause is used to express inheritance from other class specifications. The important difference from the IMPORTS clause is that in this case the components included are also inherited. That is, they are not only available for use in the new specification but also become part of their "own part". In this way, types, attributes, and operations will also be part of the new class that inherits them. The IS-SUBTYPE-OF clause defines an inheritance relationship, but unlike INHERITS, which focuses on modular reusability of specifications, it is about inheritance from a behavioral point of view, expressing subsort relationships. A concept closely related to this type of inheritance is polymorphism, where the property that an object of a subclass is also an object of the superclass is verified.

5.1.3 The DEFERRED and EFFECTIVE Clauses

These clauses allow types, attributes, and operations to be declared in complete or incomplete form. Those elements for which there is no complete definition are declared in the DEFERRED clause of a class, thus deferring the completeness of its definition, which will be completed later in its subclasses. On the other hand, elements that are either fully declared or complete an inherited definition that was previously deferred are placed in the EFFECTIVE clause. An element is considered incomplete if there are not enough axioms to define the behavior of the new operations, or if there are not enough operations to generate all possible values of the type (sort). As mentioned earlier, these clauses can contain other clauses, ATTRIBUTES, and/or TYPES that allow us to declare types, attributes, and operations, respectively. In the OPERATION clause, only the signatures of the operations are declared, and it is left to the axioms to define their semantics. In the case where the return type is Boolean, the operation is called a predicate.

Operations can also be declared as complete or partial. An operation may not be defined for the entire domain, in which case it is a partial function, and the restrictions on its domain must be specified using a precondition in the "pre" clause. A precondition is a first-order logical expression that restricts the domain to a subset of the domain's values.

In addition, Nereus allows the specification of signatures of operations in an incomplete way, using the underscore notation "_". An underscore in the operation domain expresses that subclasses can extend inherited functionality with a Cartesian product of other types. Nereus also provides a way to extend the signature of an operation. The \$ symbol refers to the inherited operation signature, and new types can be added to the cartesian product. The notation "\$" precedes the Cartesian product of the domain. The symbols _ and \$ can also be used in the axioms of the inherited class.

Nereus supports higher-order operations (a function f is higher-order if functional sorts appear in a parameter sort or in the result sort of f). In the context of collection formalization, second-order operations are required, but Nereus supports higher-order operations as well.

5.1.4 The BASIC CONSTRUCTORS Clause

The BASIC CONSTRUCTORS clause is used to specify the subset of operations that correspond to the basic constructors of the class, that is, those that allow the entire domain of the interest type to be generated.

5.1.5 The AXIOMS Clause

The AXIOMS clause is used to declare the axioms that specify the semantics of the class through first-order logical formulas. Immediately following the AXIOMS keyword are the variable declarations to be used in the axioms (at least one variable must be declared). The variable declaration consists of a list of pairs of the form $v: C$, where v is the name of a universally quantified variable of type C . An expression is a typed variable, a constant, or an application of a well-formed operation. Formulas can be atomic or compound. An atomic formula is an equivalence equation between two terms of the same type (or compatible types, depending on polymorphism). Another form of atomic formulas are inequalities, which are only available for comparable types with the specific operators. Compound formulas (or predicates) are constructed using the logical operators not, and, or, xor, implied, and equivalence.

5.1.6 Parameterized Class

In addition to the ability to define and specify simple classes, Nereus provides features to specify explicitly parameterized classes. Each class can have any number of parameters, or zero parameters if the class is not parameterized. These parameters provide enough flexibility to allow the metamodel users of the class to specify a binding between formal parameters and types for each of their instances.

In addition, Nereus provides the possibility to restrict each of these parameters to a specific type, which must be conformed by the instances, but can also be instantiated with any of its subtypes (polymorphism). If parameter types are not specified in the instantiation, Nereus assumes that they are of the special generic type ANY, which represents any value of any type in the language.

5.1.7 The LET and WHERE Clauses

Axioms can introduce local names, either to refer to common subterms or to define axioms involving second-order functions. Nereus provides the LET...IN and WHERE constructions to restrict the scope of auxiliary symbol declarations and to allow the definition of local symbols that are not visible from outside the scope delimited by such a construction.

5.1.8 The Association Clause

Nereus provides a library of relational schemas that define binary associations by type (aggregation, composition, ordinary association), degree (unary, binary), navigability (unidirectional, bidirectional), and connectivity (one-to-one, one-to-many, many-to-many).

The relationship schemas can be used to define concrete associations by instantiating classes, roles, visibility, and multiplicity. Associations can be restricted using static constraints in first-order logic. New associations can be defined using the ASSOCIATION construction. The IS clause expresses the instantiation of *<typeConstructorName>* with classes, roles, visibility, and multiplicity. The CONSTRAINED-BY clause allows static constraints to be specified in first-order logic. Figure 3 illustrates the association syntax.

```

ASSOCIATION <relationName> IS <constructorTypeName> [className1:
class1; className2: class2; roleName1: role1; roleName2: role2; m1: mult1;
m2: mult2; v1: visibility1; v2: visibility2]
CONSTRAINED-BY <constraintList>
END-ASSOCIATION

```

Figure 3: The Nereus Association Syntax

5.1.9 The rename Clause

Nereus allows defining local instances of a class in the IMPORTS, INHERITS and IS-SUBTYPE-OF clauses using the following syntax “*ClassName* [*<parameterList>*] [*<bindingList>*]” where the elements of *<parameterList>* can be pairs of class names *C1:C2*, where *C2* is an imported subspecification of *ClassName*.

5.1.10 Relation Schemes

A relation schema has basically the same syntax as a class specification, but instead of starting with the CLASS keyword, it starts with the RELATION SCHEMA keywords, and instead of ending with END-CLASS, it ends with END-RELATION. Relation schemas can be used to define concrete relationships. The possible MOF relationships (bidirectional, unidirectional, aggregation, composition) have been typified according to their multiplicities and properties. Schemas are instantiated to generate all possible associations.

5.1.11 The Package Clause

The package is the mechanism provided by Nereus for grouping related model elements to manage complexity and facilitate reuse. A package is a collection of elements of the specified metamodel. A package does not have the semantics associated with it by itself. The semantics is provided by the components of the model within it. It is possible to relate packages to each other, allowing, as in MOF, composition mechanisms and reuse of packages. Packages are related through import, generalization, and nesting relationships. The syntax for specifying packages in Nereus is shown in Figure 4.

5.2 Example: The OCL Collection

OCL Collection is the abstract supertype whose subtypes are Set, OrderedSet, Bag, and Sequence [OCL, 14]. OCL defines standard operations on collections such as *size*,

count, *includes*, *includesAll*, *isEmpty* and *notEmpty*. OCL also provides many operations on the collection types that allow us to iterate over their elements. They are *select*, *reject*, *collect*, *exists*, *forall*, and *iterate*. Figure 5 shows the Class Collection in Nereus.

```

PACKAGE packageName
IMPORTING <importsList>
GENERALIZATION <inheritsList>
NESTING <nestingList>
<elements>
END-PACKAGE

```

Figure 4: The Package Syntax

5.3 A Real-World Case: The TRACEM Metamodel

ADM standards enable the extraction of models from code representing static information. Despite the increasing interest in dynamic analysis techniques in reverse engineering, there is no standard for representing runtime information. In this section, we describe the TRACEM metamodel, a trace metamodel that is the foundation for dynamic analysis in the reverse engineering process. This metamodel complements a MDE (Model Driven Engineering) framework for software modernization that aims to integrate static and dynamic analysis techniques during the reverse engineering process [Favre, 21-b].

TRACEM is a tool for reverse engineering. It records information about how software systems behave when they are used. However, dynamic analysis requires a complete, executable system and code instrumentation to detect and record relevant events during runtime. To reverse engineer models from code, record trace data like objects, attributes, locations, types, messages, and timestamps. This dynamic information is obtained by adding code to the source code. Each time the program runs, an execution trace model is created. Then, we run the program with many test cases to get a set of trace models. These models are analyzed to obtain dynamic information that, combined with static information, allows us to improve the reverse engineering process. The resulting models are then the starting point for the forward engineering process. TRACEM allows us to specify the trace information in a standard way that supports extending and using it with other software. Figure 6 shows the TRACEM metamodel and examples of OCL constraints, which were explained in the same figure.

The main metaclasses are:

- The metaclass *Trace* is an abstract entity that encapsulates the common properties that are inherent to diverse types of traces. This class permits the model to be expanded to encompass additional types of traces, including those of interprocess communication and system-level relationships. Each instance is identified by a name, a start time, and an end time.
- An *ExecutionTrace* is a subclass of *Trace*, representing a specific execution of a program on a designated test case. Each instance is responsible for managing a set of objects and a sequence of statements that are identified during the execution of the program.

<pre> CLASS Collection [Elem] BASIC CONSTRUCTORS create, add DEFERRED TYPE Collection OPERATIONS create: -> Collection; add: Collection * Elem -> Collection; count: Collection * Elem -> Integer; EFFECTIVE OPERATIONS isEmpty: Collection -> Boolean; size: Collection -> Integer; includes: Collection * Elem -> Boolean; excludes: Collection * Elem -> Boolean; includesAll: Collection * Collection -> Boolean; excludesAll : Collection * Collection -> Boolean; forall: Collection * (Elem -> Boolean) -> Boolean; exists: Collection * (Elem -> Boolean) -> Boolean; select: Collection * (Elem -> Boolean) -> Collection; reject: Collection * (Elem -> Boolean) -> Collection; iterate: Collection * (Elem * Acc: ANY -> Acc:ANY) * (-> Acc:ANY) -> Acc:ANY; collect: Collection * (Elem -> Elem1:ANY) -> Collection; closure: Collection * (Elem-> Collection) -> Collection; AXIOMS c, c1: Collection; e, e1: Elem; f: Elem -> Boolean; g: Elem * Acc -> Acc; base: -> Acc; h:Elem -> Collection; k: Elem -> Elem1:ANY; isEmpty(c) = (size(c) = 0); iterate (create(), g, base) = base(); iterate (add(c, e), g, base)= g(e, iterate(c, g, base)); LET </pre>	<pre> OPERATION fl: Elem * Integer -> Integer; AXIOMS e1: Elem; i: Integer; fl(e1, i) = if (e = e1) then i + 1 else i endif; base() = 0; IN count(c, e) = iterate(c, fl, base) END-LET; size(create()) = 0; size(add(c, e)) = 1 + size (c); includes(create(), e) = False; includes(add(c, e), e1) = if e = e1 then True else includes(c, e1) endif; excludes(create(), e) = True; excludes(add (c, e), e1) = if e = e1 then False else excludes(c, e1) endif; includesAll(create(), c) = True; includesAll(add(c, e), c1) = includesAll(c, c1) and includes(c1, e); excludesAll(create(), c) = True; excludesAll(add(c, e), c1) = excludesAll(c, c1) and excludes(c1, e); forall (create(), f) = True; forall (add (c, e), f) = f (e) and forall(c, f); exists (create(), f) = False; exists(add (c, e), f) = f (e) or exists(c, f); select(create(), f) = create(); select(add (c, e), f) = if f (e) then add (select(c, f), e) else select(c, f) endif; reject(create(), f) = create(); reject(add (c, e), f) = if not f(e) then add(reject(c, f),e) else reject(c, f) endif; closure(create(), h) = create(); (isEmpty(h(e))) implies (closure (add(c,e),h) = closure(c, h)); (not isEmpty(h(e))) implies (closure(add(c,e), h) = add(closure(c, h), h(e))); collect(create(),k)= create(); collect (add(c,e),k) = add(collect(c, k),k(e)); END-CLASS </pre>
--	---

Figure 5: The Class Collection in Nereus

- *Location* is an abstract metaclass that represents a memory location that holds an object. The subclasses of *Location* are *LocalVariable*, *Attribute*, and *FormalParameter*. Each instance of *Location* is characterized by a name and an associated object that can be modified during program execution.
- An *ExecutionSentence* is an abstract metaclass that specifies program instructions that are executed during program execution. These include, for example, method calls, constructors, and assignments.
- An *object* is a metaclass representing objects created during program execution. Each instance has an identifier, a creation time, a destruction time, and owns attributes and objects. It can be stored in disparate locations during program execution.

--the returned object of a method call correspond to the object returned by its returned sentence
Context MethodCall:: returnedObject:Object
derived: returnedObject= subtrace.statements -> select (s| s.ocIsTypeOf(return).returnedObject
Context Assignment—restrictions on the right and left parts of an assignment
inv: right.OcIsKindOf (Location) or right.OcIsKindOf(MethodCall) or
 right.OcIsKindOf (Constructor) and left.allocatedObject =
if right.OcIsTypeOf (Constructor) **then** right.allocateObject
else if right.OcIsTypeOf (MethodCall) **then** right.returnedObject
else if right.ocIsTypeOf(Constructor) **then** right.createdObject **endif endif endif**
context Compound—compound only has local variables as locations
inv: statements -> select (s| s.ocIsTypeOf (Location) -> forAll (l | l.ocIsTypeOf (localVariable))
context MethodCall – relationship between formal and actual parameter
inv: actualParameters -> forAll (ap | self.subtrace.statements ->
 collect (ocIsTypeOf (FormalParameter)) -> exists(fp | fp.allocatedObject = ap)

Figure 6: The TRACEM metamodel in MOF

```

PACKAGE TracemMetamodel

CLASS Trace
EFFECTIVE
TYPE Trace
ATTRIBUTES
startTime: Time;
endTime: Time;
name: String;
...
END-CLASS

CLASS ExecutionTrace
IS-SUBTYPE-OF Trace
ASSOCIATES << ExecutionTrace_Object>>
<<ExecutionTrace_Statement>>
<<Call_ExecutionTrace>>
EFFECTIVE
TYPE ExecutionTrace
...
END-CLASS

CLASS Statement
...
ASSOCIATES
<<ExecutionTrace_Statement>>
<<Assignment_Statement>>
...
END-CLASS

CLASS Call
IS-SUBTYPE-OF ExecutionSentence
ASSOCIATES <<Call_ExecutionTrace>>
<<Call_Object>>
...
END-CLASS

CLASS Return
INHERITS ExecutionSentence
ASSOCIATES <<Return_Object>>
...
END-CLASS

CLASS MethodCall
IS-SUBTYPE-OF Call
ASSOCIATES <<MethodCall_Object1>>
<<MethodCall_Object2>>
<<MethodCall_Object3>>
...
AXIOMS m:Method; a1:
<<Call_ExecutionTrace>>;
a2: <<ExecutionTrace_Statement>>;
a3:<<MethodCall_Object1>>;
a4: <<MethodCall_Object2>>
a5:<<ExecutionTrace_Object>>
a6: <<Return_Object>>; a7:<<Call_Object>>

/* the returned object of a method call
corresponds to the object returned by its
returned sentence*/
get_returnedObject (a3,m) = collect (c) (select
(r) (collect (s) ( get_subtrace (a1,m),
[get_statements (a2, s)]), [oclIsTypeOf(r,
return)]), [get_returnedObject ( a6,c)])
/* relationship between formal and actual
parameter*/
forall(ap) (get_actualParameters (a7,m),
[ exists (fp) ( collect ( c ) (collect(s)
(get_subtrace(a1, m) ,[get_statements(a2,s)]),
[oclIsTypeOf ( c, FormalParameter) ]))
[allocateObject (fp) = ap])

END-CLASS

CLASS ExecutionSentence
...
IS-SUBTYPE-OF Statement
ASSOCIATES
<<Compound_ExecutionSentence>>
...
END-CLASS

CLASS Compound
IS-SUBTYPE-OF ExecutionSentence
ASSOCIATES
<<Compound_ExecutionSentence>>
...
AXIOMS c: Compound; a1:
<<Compound_Statement>>
/* compound only has local variables as
locations*/
...
END-CLASS

ASSOCIATION Call_ExecutionTrace
IS Composition-1 [ Call:Class1;
ExecutionTrace:Class2; call:role1; subtrace:
role2; 1:mult1; 1:mult2; +:visibility1;
+:visibility2]
END-ASSOCIATION

ASSOCIATION ExecutionTrace_Statement
IS Composition-3 [ ExecutionTrace: Class1;
Statement: Class2; executionTraces:role1;
statements: role2; 1: mult1; 1..*:mult2;
+:visibility1; +:visibility2]
END-ASSOCIATION

ASSOCIATION MethodCall_Object3
IS Unidirectional-1 [MethodCall:Class1;
Object: Class2; MethodCall: role1;
returnedObject: role2; 1: mult1; 0..1:mult2;+:
visibility1; +:visibility2]
END-ASSOCIATION
...
END-PACKAGE

```

Figure 7: The TRACEM Metamodel in Nereus

<pre> spec Operation [sort X] = Z1 and Z2 and ... Zr then pred f1_j : X 1 ≤ j ≤ m f2_j : X 1 ≤ j ≤ n f3_j : X 1 ≤ j ≤ k f4_j : X 1 ≤ j ≤ l base_j :-> Z_j 1 ≤ j ≤ r g_j : Z_j x X -> Z_j 1 ≤ j ≤ r end spec Collection [sort Elem] given NAT= OPERATION [Elem] then generated type Collection ::= create add (Collection ; Elem) pred isEmpty : Collection includes : Collection x Elem includesAll : Collection x Collection forAll_i : Collection 1 ≤ i ≤ k exists_i : Collection 1 ≤ i ≤ l iterate_j : Collection → Z_j 1 ≤ i ≤ r ops size : Collection → Nat select_i : Collection → Collection 1 ≤ i ≤ m </pre>	<pre> reject_i : Collection → Collection 1 ≤ i ≤ n forall c, c1 : Collection; e : Elem isEmpty (create) includes (add (c, e), e1) = if e = e1 then true else includes (c, e1) select_i (create) = create select_i (add (c, e)) = if f1_i(e) then add (select_i(c), e) else select_i(c) 1 ≤ i ≤ m includesAll (c, add (c1, e)) = includes(c, e) and includesAll (c, c1) reject_i (create) = create reject_i (add (c, e)) = if not f2_i(e) then add (reject_i(c), e) else reject_i(c) 1 ≤ i ≤ n forAll_i (add (c, e)) = f3_i(e) and forAll_i(c) 1 ≤ i ≤ k exists_i (add (c, e)) = f4_i(e) or exists_i(c) 1 ≤ i ≤ l iterate_j (create) = base_j iterate_j (add (c, e)) = g_j(e, iterate_j(c)) 1 ≤ i ≤ r local ops f2 : Elem x Nat -> Nat forall e : Elem; i : Nat f2(e, i) = i + 1 within size (c) = iterate (c, f2, 0) end-local end </pre>
--	--

Figure 8: Translating Nereus to CASL

- A *call* is an abstract metaclass that represents both method calls and constructors, where each instance is named and owns a subtrace.

More detailed information on the contribution of the TRACEM metamodel definition can be found in [Pereira, 23]. Figure 7 includes a partial specification of the metamodel TRACEM in Nereus.

6 The Nereus Semantics

The semantics of Nereus was constructively given by translating it into CASL [Bidoit, 2004]. CASL is an expressive and simple language for the formal specification of functional requirements and the modular design of software. It was developed by COFI, the international Common Framework Initiative for Algebraic Specification and Development [Hets, 25]. We chose CASL to define the semantics of Nereus because it is at the center of a family of specification languages. It can be restricted to different sublanguages and extended to higher-order, state-based, concurrent, and other languages. In addition, CASL is tool-supported and facilitates interoperability of prototyping and verification tools that link it to automatic theorem provers via HETS [Hets, 25]. It is worth noting that HETS is a parsing, static analysis, and proof management tool that combines various such tools for individual specification languages, thus providing a tool for heterogeneous multi-logic specifications. HETS is based on a graph of logic and languages (formalized as institutions), their tools, and their translations. This provides a clean semantics of heterogeneous specification and a

corresponding proof calculus. However, the CASL syntax is far from being the way to specify metadesigners. Nereus and MOF-metamodels follow similar structuring mechanisms of data abstraction and data encapsulation. We define how to automatically translate each Nereus construct into CASL, including classes, different kinds of relationships and packages. Two interesting problems linked to this translation are how to translate higher order function and associations in Nereus into CASL [Favre, 09]. We describe them below.

6.1 Translating Higher Order Operations

The classes that include higher-order operations are translated inside parameterized first-order specifications. The main difference between higher-order specifications and parameterized ones is that, in the first approach, several function-calls can be done with the same specification and parameterized specifications require the construction of several instantiations. Next, we show the translation of the Collection specification (see Figure 5) to CASL. Consider that there are as many functions f_1 , f_2 , f_3 , and f_4 as functions *select*, *reject*, *forAll* and *exists*. There are as many functions *base* and *g* as functions *iterate* too.

6.2 Translating Associations

Algebraic languages do not follow similar structuring mechanisms to UML or Nereus. The graph structure of a class diagram involves cycles such as those created by bidirectional associations. However, the algebraic specifications are structured hierarchically and cyclic import structures between two specifications are avoided. The algebraic languages do not follow these structuring mechanisms in an UML style. In UML an association can be viewed as a local part of an object. This interpretation cannot be mapped to classical algebraic specifications which do not admit cyclic import relations.

We propose an algebraic specification that considers associations belonging to the environment in which an actual instance of the class is embedded. Let *Assoc* be a bidirectional association between two classes called *A* and *B*, the following steps can be distinguished in the translation process:

- *Step 1*: Regroup the operations of classes *A* and *B* distinguishing operations local to *A*, local to *B* and, local to *A* and *B* and *Assoc*.
- *Step 2*: Construct the specifications *A'* and *B'* from *A* and *B* where *A'* and *B'* include local operations to *A* and *B* respectively.
- *Step 3*: Construct specifications *Collection[A']* and *Collection[B']* by instantiating reusable schemes.
- *Step 4*: Construct a specification *Assoc* (with *A'* and *B'*) by instantiating reusable schemes in the component *Association*
- *Step 5*: Construct the specification *AssocA+B* by extending *Assoc* with *A'*, *B'* and the operations local to *A'*, *B'* and *Assoc*.

7 How to Simulate Object-Oriented Execution Models?

An important aspect to highlight in Nereus is the ability to simulate object-oriented execution models. The basics of this are:

- Each object is described by an algebraic term.
- Associations between objects are also algebraic terms
- The axioms allow us to obtain, by rewriting, algebraic terms that describe the effect of operations.

Nereus provides the BASIC CONSTRUCTOR clause to declare the operations that generate the domain of values. When a type is declared generated, the corresponding sort is constrained to be generated by the declared constructors, which means that any value of that sort will be built by some constructor application. Next, we describe how to build specifications generated from their constructors for basic class specifications, and associations.

After identifying the generators of the domain, for each operation that is not a basic constructor, axioms are constructed over each basic constructor that generates elements of the operation domain. In the case of specifications defined from inheritance by subtype, in addition to constructing axioms for each operation that is not a basic constructor, it is also necessary to define axioms that relate the basic constructors of the supertype and those of the subtype in the hierarchy.

A generated specification is, in general, loose. Those elements for which there is no complete definition will be declared within the DEFERRED clause of a class, thus deferring the completeness of its definition that will be completed later in its subclasses. In contrast, items that are either fully declared, or complete an inherited definition, which was previously deferred, will be placed within the EFFECTIVE clause. An element will be considered incomplete when there are not enough axioms to define the behavior of the new operations, or when there are not enough operations to generate all the possible values of the type (sort).

Besides, Nereus provides a library of Relation Schemes, a typification of constructor types for MOF associations. Associations are classified according to kind (aggregation, composition, ordinary association), degree (unary, binary), navigability (unidirectional, bidirectional), and connectivity (one-to-one, one-to-many, many-to-many). An association is specified as a set of links, each link is added by applying the *addlink* operation. The component *Association* provides Relation Schemes that can be used in the definition of concrete associations by instantiating classes, roles, visibility, and multiplicity. Associations can be restricted by using static constraints in first-order logic.

The specification hierarchies, together with the specification of relationships, allow modeling object-oriented systems from a high level of abstraction being the basis for their prototyping

8 How to Construct MOF Metamodels from Nereus?

The definition of a metamodel involves first abstracting the concepts of a domain or application into the appropriate metatypes. This first level can be complemented by a graphical specification expressed by UML class diagrams and a textual specification of

Rule	NEREUS OCL
R1	v (variable) v (variable) self (if v refers the object on which the operation was called)
R2	AXIOMS assoc: AssociationName get_roleName (assoc, term) context AssociationName Translate _{OCL} (term).roleName
R3	term ₁ binaryOperator term ₂ binaryOperator (term ₁ , term ₂) Translate _{OCL} (term ₁)Translate _{OCL} (binaryOperator) Translate _{OCL} (term ₂)
R4	attributeName(term) Translate _{OCL} (term). attributeName attributeName(c) with c-> self attributeName self.attributeName
R5	OPERATIONS operationName: collectionType * (Element -> Boolean) -> collectionType AXIOMS c: collectionType; LET OPERATION f: Element -> Boolean; AXIOMS v : Element f (v)= boolean-term-with-v; IN operationName (c, f) END-LET <i>Shorthand notation</i> operationName (v) (c, [boolean-term-with-v]) with [operationName -> select reject collectionType -> Collection Set Bag Sequence OrderedSet] Translate _{OCL} (c) -> operationName (v:Element Translate _{OCL} (boolean-term-with-v) Translate _{OCL} (c) -> operationName (v Translate _{OCL} (boolean-term-with-v)) Translate _{OCL} (c) -> operationName (Translate _{OCL} (boolean-term)
R6	OPERATIONS collect: collectionType * (Element -> T1: ANY) -> Bag[T1] AXIOMS c: collectionType; LET OPERATION f: Element -> T1; AXIOMS v : Element f (v)= term-with-v IN collect (c, f) END-LET <i>Shorthand notation</i> collect (v) (c, [expr-with-v]) with collectionType -> Collection Set Bag Sequence OrderedSet Translate _{OCL} (c) -> operationName (v:Element Translate _{OCL} (term-with-v)) Translate _{OCL} (c) -> operationName (v Translate _{OCL} (term-with-v)) Translate _{OCL} (c) -> operationName (Translate _{OCL} (term))
R7	collection. propertyName collection-> collect (propertyname)

Table 1: Some rules of the Transformer NereusToMOF

the class signature in Nereus. The text of a Nereus specification is completed step by step. First, the signature and some axioms are obtained by instantiating the reusable schemas. Next, associations are transformed by instantiating reusable schemas that exist in the component *Association*. Then, a partial Nereus specification is constructed, which reflects all information of UML diagrams in the signature. The process of translating the Nereus specification into MOF metamodels annotated in OCL is supported by a system of rewrite rules for expressing basic transformations. For the sake of readability, we will denote transformation rules by *Input Scheme* and *Output Scheme* and *Applicability Conditions C*. All specification schemes in the transformation rules are supported to be syntactically and contextually correct. Table 1 contains examples of transformation rules in the format described above. The rule system allows to clearly define the correspondence between Nereus and MOF. The simple translation process results from the conceptual alignment of the Nereus metamodeling language with MOF constructions. In the following, we show how to translate some axioms of the specification of the TRACEM metamodel specification (Figure 7).

Table 2 shows the translation of the axiom Nereus of the Class *MethodCall* “*get_returnedObject (a3,m) = collect (c) (select (r) (collect (s) (get_subtrace(a1,m), [get_statements (a2, s)]), [oclIsTypeOf(r, return)]), [get_returnedObject (a6,s)])*” to the following constraint OCL (Figure 6)
 “*Context MethodCall:: returnedObject: Object
 derived: self. returnedObject= subtrace.statements ->
 select (r) r.oclIsTypeOf(return).returnedObject*”
 which will be attached to the Tracem metamodel.

9 How to Construct Nereus Specifications from MOF?

The previous section described how to generate MOF specifications from formal specifications. There are a variety of defined MOF metamodels that may need to be validated or further developed. MOF metamodels are expressed by UML class diagrams, package diagrams, and OCL specifications. In this case, it would be convenient to transform MOF metamodels into Nereus.

How to transform a UML class diagram into a signature in Nereus was described in the previous section. In this section, we will focus on transforming OCL constraints into axioms in Nereus. In the context of MOF metamodels, OCL can be associated with class invariants, pre- and post-conditions of operations, attribute constraints, and association constraints. A detailed description of MOF can be found in [Favre, 09] and [Favre, 10]. By analyzing OCL specifications, we can derive axioms that will be included in the Nereus specification.

The OCL basic types Boolean, Integer, Real and String are associated with Nereus basic types of the same name. Like OCL, Nereus provides enumeration types that are adapted to the OCL semantics. Nereus provides classes for hierarchies of enumeration types. The types Set, Bag, Sequence and Ordered Set are subtypes of Collection(x).

The transformation process from OCL specifications to Nereus is supported by a system of transformation rules. By analyzing OCL specifications, we can derive axioms that are included in the Nereus specifications. Preconditions written in OCL are used

Nereus to OCL	Rules
$get_returnedObject(a3,m) = collect(c) (select(r) (collect(s) (get_subtrace(a1,m), [get_statements(a2,s)], [oclIsTypeOf(r,return)]), [get_returnedObject(a6,c)]))$	
Translate _{OCL} (get_returnedObject(a3,m)) = Translate _{OCL} (collect(c) (select(r) (collect(s) (get_subtrace(a1,m), [get_statements(a2,s)], [oclIsTypeOf(r,return)]), [get_returnedObject(a6,c)]))	3
self.returnedObject = Translate _{OCL} (collect(c) (select(r) (collect(s) (get_subtrace(a1,m), [get_statements(a2,s)], [oclIsTypeOf(r,return)]), [get_returnedObject(a6,c)]))	1,2
self.returnedObject = Translate _{OCL} (select(r) (collect(s) (get_subtrace(a1,m), [get_statements(a2,s)], [oclIsTypeOf(r,return)])) -> collect(c) Translate _{OCL} (get_returnedObject(a6,c)))	6
self.returnedObject = Translate _{OCL} (select(r) (collect(s) (get_subtrace(a1,m), [get_statements(a2,s)], [oclIsTypeOf(r,return)])) -> collect(c) c.returnedObject)	2
self.returnedObject = Translate _{OCL} (collect(s) (get_subtrace(a1,m), [get_statements(a2,s)], [oclIsTypeOf(r,return)])) -> select(r) Translate _{OCL} (oclIsTypeOf(r,return)) -> collect(c) c.returnedObject)	5
self.returnedObject = Translate _{OCL} (get_subtrace(a1,m)) -> collect(s) Translate _{OCL} (get_statements(a2,s)) -> select(r) r.oclIsTypeOf(return) -> collect(c) c.returnedObject)	6,4
self.returnedObject = subtrace.statements -> select(r) r.oclIsTypeOf(return).returnedObject	7

Table 2: From Nereus to OCL

to generate preconditions in Nereus. Postconditions and invariants allow us to generate axioms in Nereus. The system contains a small set of about fifty rules. The set of rules has been validated by analyzing the different OCL expressions attached to the UML metamodels and MOF [MOF, 19]. Table 4 shows some rules of MOFtoNereus, in particular rules for translate OCL constraints.

Table 4 shows the translation of the OCL constraint in the class MethodCall (see Figure 6)

“actualParameters -> forAll(ap | self.subtrace.statements ->
collect(oclIsTypeOf(FormalParameter)) -> exists(fp | fp.allocatedObject = ap)”

to the following axiom in Nereus

“forAll(ap) (get_actualParameters(a7,m), [exists(fp) (collect(c) (collect(s)
(get_subtrace(a1, m), [get_statements(a2,s)],
[oclIsTypeOf(c, FormalParameter)])] [get_allocateObject(fp) = ap])”

10 Conclusion and Future Work

This article describes a unified framework for formal metamodeling in the context of MDE, specifically based on MOF. Considering that metamodeling is the essence of MDE, having secure metamodels is a prerequisite for achieving secure systems.

In this paper we show how to integrate Nereus specifications with MOF specifications. The systems *MOFtoNereus* and *NereusToMOF* allow to translate MOF from/to Nereus.

In general, metamodels initially defined as semi-formal MOF specifications are annotated with a limited repertoire of OCL constraints. Sufficient and complete formal metamodel specifications allow a broader repertoire of OCL constraints to be generated

RULE	OCL NEREUS
	<i>self can be used in the expression to refer to the object on which an operation was called, and Result is the name of the returned object, if there is one</i>
1	v. operationName (parameters) operationName (TranslateNEREUS (v),TranslateNEREUS (parameters))
2	v.attributeName attributeName (v) ----- attributeName self.attributeName attributeName (c) with c-> self
3	context AssociationName object.roleName AXIOMS a: AssociationName get_roleName (a, object)
4	Collection -> collect (v: Element expression-with-v) Let Type(expression-with-v) be S OPERATIONS collect: Collection * (Element -> Boolean) -> Collection AXIOMS LET OPERATIONS f: Element -> S AXIOMS v : Element f(v)= Translate NEREUS (expr-with-v) IN collect (collection, f) END-LET Collection -> collect (v: Element expression-with-v) Let Type(expression-with-v) be S <i>Shorthand notation</i> Collect (v) (collection, [f (v)])
5	Collection -> operationName (v boolean-expr) operationName ::= forAll exists Collection [Element] OPERATIONS operationName: Collection * (Element-> Boolean)-> Boolean AXIOMS... LET OPERATIONS f: Element -> Boolean AXIOMS v : Elem f(v)= Translate NEREUS (boolean-expr) IN operationName (collection, f) END-LET Collection -> operationName (v boolean-expr) operationName ::= forAll exists Collection [Element]
6	Collection.propertyname Collection-> collect (propertyname)

Table 3: Some rules of the Transformer MOFToNereus

OCL Constraint in to Nereus	Rules
<i>actualParameters</i> -> <i>forAll</i> (<i>ap</i> <i>self.subtrace.statements</i> -> <i>collect</i> (<i>oclIsTypeOf</i> (<i>FormalParameter</i>)) -> <i>exists</i> (<i>fp</i> <i>fp.allocatedObject</i> = <i>ap</i>))	
<i>forAll</i> (<i>ap</i>) (<i>TranslateNereus</i> (<i>actualParameters</i>), [<i>TranslateNereus</i> (<i>self.subtrace.statements</i> -> <i>collect</i> (<i>oclIsTypeOf</i> (<i>FormalParameter</i>)) -> <i>exists</i> (<i>fp</i> <i>fp.allocatedObject</i> = <i>ap</i>))]	5
<i>forAll</i> (<i>ap</i>) (<i>get_actualParameters</i> (<i>a5,m</i>), [<i>TranslateNereus</i> (<i>self.subtrace.statements</i> -> <i>collect</i> (<i>oclIsTypeOf</i> (<i>FormalParameter</i>)) -> <i>exists</i> (<i>fp</i> <i>fp.allocatedObject</i> = <i>ap</i>))]	3
<i>forAll</i> (<i>ap</i>) (<i>get_actualParameters</i> (<i>a5,m</i>), [<i>TranslateNereus</i> (<i>self.subtrace</i> -> <i>collect</i> (<i>s</i> <i>statements</i>)) -> <i>collect</i> (<i>oclIsTypeOf</i> (<i>FormalParameter</i>)) -> <i>exists</i> (<i>fp</i> <i>fp.allocatedObject</i> = <i>ap</i>))]	6
<i>forAll</i> (<i>ap</i>) (<i>get_actualParameters</i> (<i>a5,m</i>), [<i>exists</i> (<i>fp</i>) (<i>TranslateNereus</i> (<i>self.subtrace</i> -> <i>collect</i> (<i>s</i> <i>statements</i>))) -> <i>collect</i> (<i>oclIsTypeOf</i> (<i>FormalParameter</i>))], [<i>TranslateNereus</i> (<i>fp.allocatedObject</i> = <i>ap</i>)]	5
<i>forAll</i> (<i>ap</i>) (<i>get_actualParameters</i> (<i>a5,m</i>), [<i>exists</i> (<i>fp</i>) (<i>TranslateNereus</i> (<i>self.subtrace</i> -> <i>collect</i> (<i>s</i> <i>statements</i>))) -> <i>collect</i> (<i>oclIsTypeOf</i> (<i>FormalParameter</i>)))] [<i>get_allocatedObject</i> (<i>fp</i>) = <i>ap</i>]]	3
<i>forAll</i> (<i>ap</i>) (<i>get_actualParameters</i> (<i>a5, m</i>), [<i>exists</i> (<i>fp</i>) (<i>collect</i> (<i>c</i>) (<i>TranslateNereus</i> (<i>self.subtrace</i> -> <i>collect</i> (<i>s</i> <i>statements</i>))) [<i>oclIsTypeOf</i> (<i>c</i> , <i>FormalParameter</i>))], [<i>get_allocatedObject</i> (<i>fp</i>) = <i>ap</i>]]	4, 1
<i>forAll</i> (<i>ap</i>) (<i>get_actualParameters</i> (<i>a5,m</i>), [<i>exists</i> (<i>fp</i>) (<i>collect</i> (<i>c</i>) (<i>collect</i> (<i>s</i>) (<i>get_subtrace</i> (<i>a1,m</i>), [<i>get_statements</i> (<i>a2,s</i>)]) [<i>oclIsTypeOf</i> (<i>c</i> , <i>FormalParameter</i>))], [<i>get_allocatedObject</i> (<i>fp</i>) = <i>ap</i>)]	4,2

Table 4: From OCL to Nereus

implementations. When metamodels have semantics, they are formal specifications and can be used to analyze, validate, and refine themselves and the family of instances they define. We show how to integrate Nereus specifications with MOF specifications. The systems *MOFtoNereus* and *NereusToMOF* allow to translate MOF from/to Nereus. In general, metamodels initially defined as semi-formal MOF specifications are annotated with a limited repertoire of OCL constraints. Formal metamodel specifications allow a broader repertoire of OCL constraints to be generated in metamodels that are used to generate implementations.

The MOF metamodel is self-descriptive, meaning that it is formally defined using its own metamodel constructs. A powerful aspect of MOF metamodels is that if the complexity of systems and applications over the years makes it necessary to work with higher levels of abstraction, the metamodels could be defined from architectures with more than 4 levels. Transformations between them could also be defined, and of course the Nereus formalism, like MOF, would also allow this.

The Nereus language has evolved over the years. The evolution was supported by a set of tools implemented for experimentation. They have been described in [Favre, 16]. The industrial use of these results would require the complete development of a Nereus modeling framework that applies these results for the creation of models and metamodels with facilities for automatic code generation.

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